

Title: Improving Sexual Education in Schools: A Scoping Review Protocol

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Abstract:

This research project addresses the need to improve sexual education in schools, particularly from the perspective of adolescents. Motivated by dissatisfaction among Norwegian students, the study aims to explore existing research on sexual education and instructional programs. The protocol outlines a scoping review with a clear PICO framework, a planned search process, and the use of PRISMA-ScR (Tricco et al., 2018) and Arksey & O'Malley (Arksey & O'Malley, 2005) methods. The goal is to identify current programs and literature informing how school health services can contribute to promoting positive sexual health among children and young people.

Introduction:

For this study, we intend to use the scoping review method to investigate the topic of sexual education in schools by school nurses. We will apply the frameworks developed by Arksey & O'Malley (2005) and rely on guidelines for presentations of scoping reviews by Tricco et al. (2018), PRISMA-ScR (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses Extension for Scoping Reviews). As a form of knowledge synthesis, we aim to identify trends and knowledge gaps in existing literature, informing practice, research, and guidelines. The frameworks provide a structured approach to identifying research questions, developing protocols, search strategies, study selection, data extraction, analysis of findings, and reporting results. We emphasize the importance of transparency throughout the research process.

Framework stage one: Identifying the research question.

Background and Research Purpose: Discontent among Norwegian students with the current sexual education has driven this study. The dissatisfaction and gaps initially identified led us to investigate previous research on sexual education and instructional programs. We aim to provide an overview of existing research on sexual education and instructional programs to contribute to improvement efforts. The purpose is to identify positive approaches and address existing knowledge gaps.

Purpose of the Study: Our study aims to provide an overview of how school nurses contribute to promoting positive and safe sexuality among children and young people through sexual education. The research question guiding our study is as follows:

What sexual education programs exist today, and what does the literature say about how school nurses promote positive and safe sexuality in children and young people through sexual education?

Framework stage two: Identifying relevant studies

Search Strategy:

The search strategy aims to identify both published and unpublished studies. An initial search in Google Scholar has been undertaken to identify articles on this topic, followed by analyses of the text words contained in titles and abstracts, and index terms used to describe these articles. This informed the development of a PICO and search strategy. PICO and a full search strategy of the databases are detailed below, including our inclusion and exclusion criteria. Furthermore, reference lists of included studies will be screened for additional studies.

P	I	C	O
Barn	Seksualundervisning	Implementerte seksualundervisning programmer	Positiv seksualitet
Unge	Sexual education		Trygg seksualitet
Adolescents	Sex education	Seksualundervisningsopplegg	
Adolescent	Sexual health education	- Spør først - Alt i meg	Sexual health
Children		CSE (comprehensive sexual education)	Health promotion
Child			(Sexual behavior)
Helsesykepleier		Sexual education programs	
Public health nurse		Sex education programs	Attitudes
Community health nurse			Holdninger
School nurse			
School health services			
Child health nurse			

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Inclusion and exclusion criteria

Inclusion Criteria:

Study Design: All types of literature, encompassing academic papers, scientific literature, research articles, books, guidelines, news articles, and social media content.

Population: Youth and children (0-18 years).

Exposure: Sexual education.

Outcome: *Sexual education programs and* promotion of positive sexuality.

Publication Years: Limited to the last 10 years initially, with the possibility of extending the timeframe if an insufficient number of relevant studies are identified.

Country/Context: School setting. Uncertainty regarding the specific country.

Language: Scandinavian languages and English.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Sexual education delivered outside the school setting.
- Studies involving parents, adults, or the elderly.

We conducted searches in four databases: Epistemonikos, Medline, Cinahl, and EMBASE. The searches were based on our PICO framework and tailored to the specific characteristics of each database. Presented below is the search strategy employed in Cinahl.

barn OR unge OR ungdom OR (adolescents or teenagers or young adults or teen or youth)
OR (children or adolescents or youth or child or teenager) OR helsesykepleier OR (public
health nurse or community health nurse or district nurse) OR (school health nurse or school
nursing or school nurse) OR (school health services and adolescent health and health
education and self care) OR child health nurse
seksualundervisning OR (sexual education or sex education or sex ed) OR sexual health
education
seksualundervisningsprogram OR seksualundervisningsopplegg OR comprehensive sex
education OR comprehensive sexual education OR sexual education program* OR sex
education program*
positiv seksualitet OR trygg seksualitet OR sexual health OR sexual health promotion OR
sexual behavior OR (attitudes or perceptions) OR holdninger

Limitations: Publication Date 2013-2023

Framework stage three: Study selection

Two master students will be the main reviewers and will read all references separately. Independent of each other, they will read titles and abstracts identified through the literature searches. They will be evaluated according to the inclusion criteria. Studies that the reviewers agree seem relevant will be considered in full text, and thereafter either included or excluded, in accordance with the inclusion criteria. Any disagreements between the reviewers will be resolved by discussion and, if necessary, by involving a third researcher. All studies we agree to meet all the inclusion criteria will be included in the scoping review. To help with this process we use Rayyan systematic review software (Strømme, 2020).

Framework stage four: Charting the data (Data Extraction)

We will systematically extract the following information from the included studies: the name of the programme and its characteristics (including area of use, year of publication, content, purpose, method), research questions in the study, study design, study context, country, characteristics of participants and users, as well as the authors' conclusions about the programme properties. We will use a pre-designed data extraction form, which will be piloted.

The researchers will individually extract data from the included studies, and thereafter switch to check the information. Any disagreements will be resolved by discussion. No quality assessment of the included studies will be performed.

Framework stage five: Collating, summarizing and reporting the results

Scoping reviews, while sharing some similarities with systematic reviews, differ significantly by not evaluating the quality of included studies or presenting generalizable findings. The focus is on providing an overview of all reviewed material. Scoping studies include no systematic synthesis of individual study results (e.g. no meta-analysis), but they provides an overview and description of existing literature. We will consider the meaning of the findings

and how they relate to the overall study purpose; thereby discussing implications for future research, practice and policy.

We will sort and present the included studies in categories related to the extracted characteristics of included studies, such as the overall number of studies included, types of study design, year of publication, characteristics of the study population, and countries where studies were conducted (Levac et.al 2010). We will employ a descriptive and thematic analysis of the extracted data, presenting results in text and tables. The analysis aims to identify patterns and themes across different sources to add meaning to the study's findings. We will give mainly narrative presentations of results and conclusions. We will also try to evaluate the results across the different studies to investigate if there are any patterns in findings and conclusions.

This scoping study will rely on guidelines for presentations of scoping reviews by Tricco et.al. (2018), and PRISMA-ScR (Tricco et al., 2018).

Ethical Considerations:

As our study does not involve the handling of personal or sensitive information, confidentiality is not a relevant concern. Transparency is a key focus throughout the research process. We adhere to general research ethics guidelines developed by the National Committees for Research Ethics (De nasjonale forskningsetiske komiteene, 2019), aiming to enable accurate replication of our searches and methods for other researchers.

Timeframe:

- Weeks 47-48: Consultation session with a librarian for assistance with literature search.
- Week 49: Prepare a draft of the project description for review by the supervisor. Conduct searches on Google Scholar and review articles to identify additional terms for PICO and search criteria. Evaluate feedback from the supervisor and make necessary revisions.
- Week 50: Finalize the search strategy and conduct searches, except gray literature. Establish post-hoc inclusion and exclusion criteria. Submit the project description. Receive guidance on finalizing the protocol.

- Week 51: Complete the protocol.
- Weeks 51-4: Conduct searches of grey literature. Review relevant articles. This timeline is tentative and may be reassessed based on the volume of findings.
- Weeks 5-10: Initiate the first draft of the thesis and article.
- Week 11: Submit the initial draft to the supervisor for review.
- Weeks 12-15: Review and incorporate feedback from the supervisor.
- Weeks 16-19: Finalize the master's thesis.
- Week 20: Submit the master's thesis by May 15, 2024.
- Week 21: Submit the article to the journal.

Conclusion:

This scoping review protocol outlines our plan to investigate sexual education in schools with a focus on the role of school nurses. The dissatisfaction among Norwegian students and teachers underscores the need for improvements in sexual education programs. By employing the scoping review method, we aim to provide a comprehensive overview of existing research, identifying gaps and potential areas for improvement. Our study contributes to the ongoing discourse on sexual education, guiding future efforts to enhance positive and safe sexuality among children and young people.

Keywords: Sexual education, school nurses, adolescents, scoping review, PICO, systematic review, Arksey & O'Malley, PRISMA-ScR, literature review, sexual health, curriculum, instructional programs, youth, Norway, education quality.

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